

Forecasting the Chances of Having Cardiovascular Disease in Patients Using Data Mining Tool

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Abstract--In the framework of the health-care system, health issues are tremendous in this current environment, particularly cardiac illnesses as a result of altered lifestyles such as eating habits and lack of exercise. The data mining sector comprised the prediction and detection of anomaly, as well as the discovery of relevant patterns for future research and their risk rate in these areas, employing algorithms classification systems. Today the health industry holds hidden information essential for decision-making.

Keywords — Weka, Cardio Vascular Disease, Data mining, attributes, algorithms, accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION:

The health business has a lot of data, but manually mining it is time intensive, and there's a lot of data that isn't mined at all, which is necessary for finding hidden patterns and making good decisions. Discovery of hidden patterns and relationships are the key feature for predicting the future, often this feature goes unexploited. Using clinical profiles together with age, sex, blood stress and blood sugar and it predict the likelihood of patients getting heart disease [6].

II. DESCRIPTION

Heart disease refers to a variety of conditions that affect your coronary heart disease. Blood vessel illnesses, such as coronary artery disease; heart rhythm issues (arrhythmias); and congenital heart abnormalities, to name a few, are all covered within the heart disease umbrella. The indications and symptoms differ depending on whether you're a woman or a man. Men, for example, are more prone to have chest pain, but women are more prone to have additional signs and symptoms in addition to chest pain, such as shortness of breath, nausea, and extreme tiredness.

The “coronary heart attack” is regularly used interchangeably with the time period "cardiovascular disease." Cardiovascular ailment generally refers to the situations that comprise some narrowed or blocked blood vessels which could result in a heart attack, chest ache (angina) or stroke, different coronary heart situations, along side those that have an impact on your coronary heart's muscle, valves or rhythm, also are taken into consideration styles of heart ailment. You may not be identified any cardiovascular problem till you have got a heart assault, angina, stroke or coronary heart failure. It is critical to look at for cardiovascular symptoms and talk about the fact together with your physician.

Key facts

- Cardio Vascular sickness (CVDs) are the foremost motive of demise globally: more human beings die yearly from CVDs than from any other purpose.
- CVDs claimed the lives of 17.9 million individuals worldwide in 2016, accounting for 31% of all fatalities. Heart attacks and strokes account for 85 percent of these fatalities.
- Over 3 quarters of CVD deaths take location in low- and middle-earnings countries.
- In 2015, 82 percent of the 17 million premature deaths (before the age of 70) owing to no communicable illnesses occurred in low- and middle-income countries, with CVDs accounting for 37 % [2].

Data mining

Data mining is a manner utilized by agencies to reveal raw information into beneficial information through the usage

of a few software software to look for patterns in huge batches of facts, enterprise and educate more about their customers to expand more powerful advertising and thier advertising techniques, increase revenue and decrease costs.

Data mining tactics are used to construct system gaining knowledge or machine learning models that strength applications along with search engine technology and website advice applications [3].

commonly used functionalities include Data cleansing, Artificial intelligence (AI), Association rule learning, Clustering, Classification, Data analytics, Data warehousing, Machine learning, Regression.

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This record is to analyse the reason of cardiac sickness in human beings through searching through one-of-a-kind statistics sets and with the aid of using mining tools we are predicting the disease with greater accuracy. The dataset used in this observe has 14 functions, one goal variable, and 303 times in which 138 suffers from cardiovascular ailment and one hundred sixty five are healthful topics. we are the usage of this data sets to teach a dataset and discover the correct algorithms and its accuracy and design a appropriate model for checking out [5]”.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study is about the process of analysing and producing patterns from medical records of patients with CVDs, as well as detecting and producing patterns from disease behaviour using algorithms and data mining tools. Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis was utilised as a development tool (weka).

Weka

Weka is a collection of gadget gaining knowledge of software program advanced on the college of Waikato, New Zealand. the program is written in Java. It contains a set of visualization equipment and algorithms for statistics evaluation and predictive modelling coupled with graphical consumer interface. Weka helps several general information mining tasks, greater specially, facts pre-processing, clustering, classification, regress ion, visualization, and function selection tools in order that we are able to expand system learning techniques and follow them to actual-international data mining issues[3].

Properties of weka

- The new machine learning schemes also can be developed with this bundle.
- The raw statistics collected from the sphere may additionally contain several null values and inappropriate fields.
- The data pre-processing tools provided in weka helps to cleanse the data in the datasets.
- Save the pre-processed data in your local storage for applying ML algorithms.
- Next, depending on the kind of ML model that are trying to develop we can select one of the options such as Classify, Cluster, Associate etc.
- The Attributes choice lets in the automatic choice of features to create a discounted dataset.
- Under each category, WEKA provides the implementation of several algorithms. We can select an algorithm of our choice, set the desired parameters and run it on the dataset.
- Then, WEKA would give you the statistical output of the model processing.
- It gives you a visualization tool to look into the information.[4]

V. IMPLEMENTATION

We're using three different algorithms on a particular data set to construct or extract an usable model for predicting the severity of coronary heart disease in a person in a certain setting.

Data source

Here we consider the dataset from Kaggle repository, which contains 303 instances and 14 attributes. The prediction of heart disease is based on several parameters.

The statistics set from Kaggle repository incorporates the attributes of signs and symptoms or behaviour of human frame with a recognised target magnificence. This records set is used as education statistics for the classifier. [4]

Table 1: Attributes and its values

Input Attributes	Function/ Values
age	age in years
sex	sex (1 = male; 0 = female)
cp	chest pain type Value 1 typical angina Value 2 atypical angina Value 3

	non-anginal pain Value 4 asymptomatic
rtbps	resting blood pressure (in mm Hg on admission to the hospital)
chl	serum cholestorl in mg/dl
fbsl	(fasting blood sugar > 120 mg/dl) (1 = true; 0 = false)
restecr	resting electrocardiographic results Value 0 normal Value 1 having ST-T wave abnormality (T wave inversions and/or ST elevation or depression of > 0.05 mV) Value 2 showing probable or definite left ventricular hypertrophy by Estes' criteria
maxhr	maximum heart rate achieved
exang	Exercise induced angina (1 = yes; 0 = no).
oldpeak	ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest
slope	the slope of the peak exercise ST segment Value 1 up-sloping Value 2 flat Value 3 down-sloping
col	number of major vessels (0-3) coloured by fluoroscopy
hr	3 = normal; 6 = fixed defect; 7 = reversible defect
num	diagnosis of heart disease(angiographic disease status) Value 0< 50% diameter narrowing Value1> 50% diameter narrowing.

Algorithms

Decision Tree: Decision Tree algorithm belongs to the family of supervised learning algorithms. Unlike other supervised learning algorithms, the decision tree algorithm can be used for solving regression and classification problems too.

The intention of using a decision Tree is to create a training model that could use to predict the class or cost of the goal variable via getting to know easy choice guidelines inferred from earlier information (training information). In decision Tree, for predicting a category label for a document we begin from the basis of the tree. we are comparing the values of the basis attribute with the record characteristic. On the basis of comparison, we observe the branch corresponding to that price and bounce to the subsequent

node.

Figure1: Summary for test modal using Decision Tree

Random Tree: The random trees classifier, unlike the Support Vector Machine (SVM), can handle a mix of categorical and numerical variable. Random Trees are also less susceptible to data scaling, whereas SVM frequently requires data to be normalised before training or classification [7].

When the training set is short or uneven, however, SVM is said to perform better. Random Trees is a considerably less computationally costly classifier than SVM, and it works better and faster with large training sets.

The Random Trees method is available in a variety of forms. The implementation of the Gini Impurity index is used by the object analyst to evaluate what is an acceptable split point for a node on the classification tree, as well as the minimum number of samples, maximum tree depth, and tree accuracy as terminating criteria.

Figure2: Summary for test modal using Random Tree

Random Forest: Random forest is a learning method that is supervised. It creates a "forest" out of an ensemble of

decision trees, which are commonly trained using the "bagging" approach. The bagging method's basic premise is that combining several learning models improves the final output. [8]

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Incorrectly Classified Instances 303      100 %
Correctly Classified Instances  0         0 %
Gini statistic                   1
Mean absolute error              0.0957
Root mean squared error          0.1297
Relative absolute error          19.2875 %
Root relative squared error      26.038 %
Total Number of Instances       303

== Detailed Accuracy By Class ==
      TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall   F-Measure  MCC   ROC Area  PRC Area  Cla:
1.000  0.000  1.000    1.000  1.000    1.000  1.000  1.000  0
1.000  0.000  1.000    1.000  1.000    1.000  1.000  1.000  1
Weighted Avg.  1.000  0.000  1.000    1.000  1.000    1.000  1.000  1.000

== Confusion Matrix ==
  a  b  <-- Classified as
38  0 | a = 0
 0 145 | b = 1
    
```

Figure3: Summary for test modal using Random Forest

Table 2: Result before filtration

Techniques	Accuracy	Time
Decision Algorithm (j48)	93.7294 %	0.01
Random Tree	100 %	0.08
Random Forest	100 %	0.07

We were able to increase the accuracy of the decision tree to 94.0594 percent after applying some filtration to the attribute, which is only about 0.38 % increase in values. Since it has a value close to 95 %, we can use this algorithm, but the other two algorithms outperform the decision tree algorithm.

Table 3: Result after filtration

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We see that the highest accuracy for the training set is achieved Random Tree and random forest which is identical to 100%.

VI. CONCLUSION

Data mining algorithms are used to uncover hidden knowledge in a set of disorder data, which may then be utilised to analyse and predict how illnesses will behave in the future. One of the statistics mining methodologies for assigning a class label to a group of unclassified cases is classification.

The employment of specific algorithms and mixes of various highly essential features for this Coronary heart disease prediction using data mining is the focus of this article. With the use of 14 characteristics, Random Tree and Decision Forest Tree outperformed with 100 % accuracy.

Furthermore, the algorithm Random Forest, which has a 100% accuracy rate and a performance time of 0.07, has an advantage over the Random Tree. Only the default parameters are used to implement the algorithms.

VII. REFERENCES:

- [1] <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseasesconditions/heart-disease/>
- [2] <https://www.who.int/news>
- [3] <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/datamining>
- [4] Aditya Methaila , Prince Kansal , Himanshu Arya , Pankaj Kumar 1NetajiSubhas Institute of Technology,India and 2 Student, B.Tech (CSE), Maharaja Surajmal Institute of Technology New Delhi, India :“EARLY HEART DISEASE “
- [5] Basma Saleh, Ahmed Saedi, Ali alAqbi, Lamees Salman, "Analysis of Weka Data Mining Techniques for Heart Disease Prediction System".
- [6] Aditya Methaila, P. Kansal, P. Kumar, Computer Science, "Early Heart Disease Prediction Using Data Mining Techniques"
- [7] https://www.pcigeomatics.com/geomaticahelp/concepts/focus_c/oa_classif_intro_rt.html
- [8] <https://builtin.com/data-science/random-forest-algorithm>.